

>Seq122821h4	Nt	Note
gactccccacattctctctgaagggatcacttttcgaaagg	41	Intron 3
gggaaatccctgggaggttgcgatgagtttgaaccagctgcctcacctggaagtgctg	101	Intron 3
cctacagtctgaccttggtttggcaggtggatgcagatgacgtcatgactaaagaggaa	161	hP1R
cagatcttctgtctgcaccgtgctcaggcccagtgcgaaaacggctcaaggaggtcctg	221	hP1R
cagaggccagccagcataatggaatcagacaagggatggacatctgcgtccacatcaggg	281	hP1R
aagcccaggaagataaagcatctgggaagctctacccttacgatggtccggactacgcg	341	hP1R
gcaccactggcagcaggtaccgagggcggcctgtctgcggaaatgggaccacatcctg	401	hP1R
tgctggccgctggggcaccaggtgaggtggtgctgtgcctgtccggactacatttat	461	hP1R
gacttcaatcacaaggccatgcctaccgacgctgtgaccgcaatggcagctgggagctg	521	hP1R
gtgctgggcacaaacaggacgtgggccaactacagcgagtgtgtcaaatttctcaccaat	581	hP1R
gagactcgtgaacgggaggtgtttgaccgctgggcatgatttacaccgtgggctactcc	641	hP1R
gtgtccctggcgtccctcaccgtagctgtgctcatcctggcctacttttaggggctgcac	701	hP1R
tgcacgcgaactacatccacatgcacctgttctgtccttcatgctgcgcgccgtgagc	761	hP1R
atcttcgtaaggagcgtgtgcttactctggcggcaccgcttgatgaggtgagcgctc	821	hP1R
accgaggaggagctgcgcggccatcgcccaggcgccccgcggcctgccaccgcccgtgcc	881	hP1R
ggctacgcgggctgcaggtggctgtgaccttcttcttacttctggccaccaactac	941	hP1R
tactggattctgtggaggggctgtacctgcacagcctcacttcatggccttctctca	1001	hP1R
gagaagaagtacctgtgggcttcacagctctcggctggggtctgccgctgtcttcgtg	1061	hP1R
gctgtgtgggtcagtgctcagagctaccctggccaacaccgggtgctgggacttgagctcc	1121	hP1R
gggaacaaaaagtggatcatccaggtgcccatcctggcctccatgtgctcaacttcate	1181	hP1R
ctcttcatcaatatcgtccgggtgctcggcaccagctgcgggagaccaacgccggccgg	1241	hP1R
tgtgacacacggcagcagtagccgaagctgctcaaatccacgctgggtgctcatgccctc	1301	hP1R
tttggcgtccactacattgtcttcatggccacaccatacaccgaggtctcagggacgctc	1361	hP1R
tggcaagtccagatgcactatgagatgctcttcaactccttcagggttttttgtcgca	1421	hP1R
atcatatactgtttctgcaatggcgaggtacaagctgagatcaagaaatcttgagccgc	1481	hP1R
tggacactggcactggacttcaagcgaaaggcacgcagcgggagcagcagctatagctac	1541	hP1R
ggccccatggtgtccacacaaagtgtgaccaatgtcggccccctgtgggactcggcctg	1601	hP1R
ccccctcagccccgcctactgccactgccaccaccaacggccaccctcagctgctggc	1661	hP1R
catgccaagccagggaccccagccctggagaccctogagaccacaccacctgccatggct	1721	hP1R
gtccccaaaggacgatgggttctcacaacgctcctgctcaggcctggacgagggcctct	1781	hP1R
gggctgagcggccacctgcctgctacaggaagagtgggagacagtcatggaTCCCTCA	1841	hP1R
GGTGCAGGCTGCCTATCAGAAGGTGGTGGCTGGTGGCCAATGCCCTGGCTCACAAATA	1901	rbGPA
CCACTGAGATCTTTTTCCCTCTGCCAAAAATTATGGGGACATCATGAAGCCCCTTGAGCA	1961	rbGPA
TCTGACTTCTGGCTAATAAAGGAAATTTATTTTCATTGCAATAGTGTGTTGGAATTTTTT	2021	rbGPA
GTGTCTCTCACTCGGAAGGACATATGGGAGGGCAAATCATTTAAAACATCAGAATGAGTA	2081	rbGPA
TTTGGTTTLAGAGTTTGGCAACATATGCCCATATGCTGGCTGCCATGAACAAAGTTGGCT	2141	rbGPA
ATAAAGAGGTCATCAGTATATGAACAGCCCCCTGCTGTCCATTCTTATTCCATAGAAA	2201	rbGPA
AGCCTTGACTTGAGGTTAGATTTTTTTTATATTTTGTGTTGTTATTTTTTCTTTAAC	2261	rbGPA
ATCCCTAAAATTTCTTTACATGTTTTACTAGCCAGATTTTTCTCTCTCTGACTACT	2321	rbGPA
CCCAGTCATAGCTGTCCCTCTTCTTTATGGAGATCCTcGAGGGACCTAATAACTTCGTA	2381	SDA/LOXP
TAGCATACATTATACGAAGTTATATTAAGGTTATTTGAATATGATCGGAATTGGGCTGCA	2441	SDA/LOXP
GGAATTCGATAGCTTGGCTGCAGGTCGACGTACGTAGCAAGCTTGATGGGCCCTGGTACC	2501	Intron 4
aCGGGGTCCAGTGGATTAGATGGGGTTGGGCAAGCCAGGGACTTTGCTGAGGGCgCTG	2561	Intron 4
GtCCaaacaggtgggctgGGCCAACCTTCCTTAAGAGA	2600	Intron 4

Figure S-1 Nucleotide Sequence of hPTH1R KI region. The sequence was obtained by Sanger sequence analysis of PCR products generated using the primers shown in Table S1. Nucleotide position number (Nt) and sequence corresponding to mouse Intron3 (blue), hPTH1R cDNA (green), rabbit beta globin poly A (gold), a vector-derived self-deleting anchor containing a LOX-P site (black) and mouse intron 4 (purple) are indicated in the righthand columns.

Clustal O align Mouse P1R vs human P1R-HA		nT
hPTHR1-HA	MGTARIAPGLALLCCPVLSSAYALVDADDVMTKEEQIFLLHRAQAQCEKRLKEVLQRPA	60
MOUSE_PTHR1_Q91WV4	MGTARIAPSLALLCCPVLSSAYALVDADDVFTKEEQIFLLHRAQAQCDKLLKEVLHTAA	60
	*****.*****:*****:* *****: *	
hPTHR1-HA	SIMESDKGWTSASTSGKPRKDKASGKLYPYDVDPDYAAPTGSRYRGRPCLEWDHILCWPL	120
MOUSE_PTHR1_Q91WV4	NIMESDKGWTSPASTSGKPRKEKAPGKFPESKENKDVPTGSRRRRGRPCLEWDNIVCWPL	120
	.***** *****:* **:* . : .***** *****:***:****	
hPTHR1-HA	GAPGEVAVPCPDYIYDFNHKGHAYRRCDRNGSWELVPGHNRTWANYSECVKFLTNETRE	180
MOUSE_PTHR1_Q91WV4	GAPGEVAVPCPDYIYDFNHKGHAYRRCDRNGSWEVVPGHNRWANYSECLKFMTNETRE	180
	*****:*****:***:*****	
hPTHR1-HA	REVFDRLGMIYTVGYSVSLASLTVAVLILAYFRRLHCTRNYIHMHLFLSFMRAVSIQVK	240
MOUSE_PTHR1_Q91WV4	REVFDRLGMIYTVGYSMSLASLTVAVLILAYFRRLHCTRNYIHMHLFLSFMRAVSIQVK	240
	*****:*****:*****:*****.*****	
hPTHR1-HA	DAVLYSGATLDEAERLTEEELRAIAQPPPPATAAAGYAGCRVAVTFFLYFLATNYIWIL	300
MOUSE_PTHR1_Q91WV4	DAVLYSGFTLDEAERLTEEELHIAQVPPPPAAAAGYAGCRVAVTFFLYFLATNYIWIL	300
	***** *****: **,***:*:*.*****:*****	
hPTHR1-HA	VEGLYLHSLIFMAFFSEKYLWGFTVFGWGLPAVFAVWVSVRATLANTGCWDLSSGNKK	360
MOUSE_PTHR1_Q91WV4	VEGLYLHSLIFMAFFSEKYLWGFTVFGWGLPAVFAVWVSVRATLANTGCWDLSSGHKK	360
	*****:*****.*****:*****:***	
hPTHR1-HA	WIIQVPILASIVLNFILFINIVRVLATKLRNAGRCDRQQYRKLKSTLVLMPLFGVH	420
MOUSE_PTHR1_Q91WV4	WIIQVPILASVVLNFILFINIRVLAATKLRNAGRCDRQQYRKLKSTLVLMPLFGVH	420
	*****:*****:*****:*****:*****:*****	
hPTHR1-HA	YIVFMATPYTEVSGTLWQVQMHYEMLFNSFQGFVVAIYCFCNQEVQAEIKKSWSRWTLA	480
MOUSE_PTHR1_Q91WV4	YTVFMALPYTEVSGTLWQIQMHYEMLFNSFQGFVVAIYCFCNQEVQAEIRKSWSRWTLA	480
	* **** *****:*****:*****	
hPTHR1-HA	LDFKRRKARSGSSSYSGPMVSHTSVTNVGPRVGLGLPLSPRLLPATTTNGHPQLPGHAKP	540
MOUSE_PTHR1_Q91WV4	LDFKRRKARSGSSSYSGPMVSHTSVTNVGPRAGLSLPLSSRLLPATTTNGHSQPLPGHAKP	539
	*****.***.***** *****: ***** *****	
hPTHR1-HA	GTPALETLETTPPAMAAPKDDGFLNGSCSGLDEEASGPERPPALLQEEWETVM*	593
MOUSE_PTHR1_Q91WV4	GAPAIEN-ETIPVTMTVPKDDGFLNGSCSGLDEEASGARPPPLLQEEWETVM*	591
	*:***. ** * :*:.***** ***** *****	

Figure S-3. Alignment of mouse PTH1R and human PTH1R-HA protein sequences. An * (asterisk) below the paired sequence lines indicate identical amino acids; a : (colon) indicates amino acids with groups of strongly similar properties, and a . (period) indicates amino acids with weakly similar properties. The HA tag is in red font. The mature human PTH1R is comprised of an N-terminal extracellular domain (ECD; residues Y23-E182); a transmembrane domain region (TMD; residues V183-C462) and a C-terminal tail (N463-M593).

BLAST Alignment of Intron-3 region with mouse PTH1 Intron 3 region	
Mus musculus strain C57BL/6J chromosome 9, GRCm39	
Sequence ID: NC 000075.7	
gene="Pth1r" parathyroid hormone 1 receptor	
Length: 124359700	
Range 1: 110560709 to 110560836	
Query 1	GACTCCCCACATTCTCTCTGAAGGGATCACATTTTCGAAAGGGGGAAATCCCTGGGGAGG 60
Sbjct 110560836	GACTCCCCACATTCTCTCTGAAGGGATCACATTTTCGAAAGGGGGAAATCCCTGGGGAGG 11056
Query 61	TTGCATGAGTTTGAACACAGCTGCCTCACCTGGAAGTGTGCCTACAGTCTGACCTTTGG 120
Sbjct 110560776	TTGCATGAGTTTGAACACAGCTGCCTCACCTGGAAGTGTGCCTACAGTCTGACCTTTGG 11056
Query 121	TTTGGCAG 128
Sbjct 110560716	TTTGGCAG 110560709
BLAST Alignment of Intron-4 region with mouse PTH1 gene Intron 4 region	
Mus musculus strain C57BL/6J chromosome 9, GRCm39	
Sequence ID: NC 000075.7	
gene="Pth1r" parathyroid hormone 1 receptor	
Length: 124359700	
Range 1: 110560172 to 110560270	
Query 1	ACGGGGTCCCAGTGGATTAGATGGGGTTGGCAAGCCAGGGACTTTGCTGAGGGCGCTG 60
Sbjct 110560270	ACGGGGTCCCAGTGGATTAGATGGGGTTGGCAAGCCAGGGACTTTGCTGAGGGCGCTG 110560211
Query 61	GTCCAAACAGGGTGGGCTGGCCAACTTCCTTAAAGAGA 99
Sbjct 110560210	GTCCAAACAGGGTGGGCTGGCCAACTTCCTTAAAGAGA 110560172
BLAST Alignment of rbG-PA with rabbit beta globin gene poly A region	
Oryctolagus cuniculus breed Thorbecke inbred chromosome 1, OryCun2.0	
Sequence ID: NC 013669.1	
Length: 194850757	
hemoglobin subunit beta-1/2 isoform 1x	
gene="HBB2" hemoglobin, beta	
Query 1	TCCTCAGTGCAGGTCGCCATCAGAAAGTGGTGGCTGGTGGCCAAATGCCCTGGCTCA 60
Sbjct 146237182	TCCTCAGTGCAGGTCGCCATCAGAAAGTGGTGGCTGGTGGCCAAATGCCCTGGCTCA 146237123
Query 61	CAAAATACCAGTGCAGATCTTTTCCTCTGCCAAAATTTATGGGGACATCATGAAGCCCT 120
Sbjct 146237122	CAAAATACCAGTGCAGATCTTTTCCTCTGCCAAAATTTATGGGGACATCATGAAGCCCT 146237063
Query 121	TGAGCATCTGACTTCTGGCTaataaaggaaatttttttattttcattgcaatAGTGTGTGGAA 180
Sbjct 146237062	TGAGCATCTGACTTCTGGCTAATAAAGGAAATTTATTTTCATTGCAATAGTGTGTGGAA 146237003
Query 181	TTTTTTGTGTCTCACTCGGAAGGACATATGGGAGGCAAAATCATTAAAACATCAGAA 240
Sbjct 146237002	TTTTTTGTGTCTCACTCGGAAGGACATATGGGAGGCAAAATCATTAAAACATCAGAA 146236943
Query 241	TGAGTATTTGGTTTAGAGTTTGGCAACATATGCCCATATGCTGGTGCATGAACAAAG 300
Sbjct 146236942	TGAGTATTTGGTTTAGAGTTTGGCAACATATGCCCATATGCTGGTGCATGAACAAAG 146236883
Query 301	TTGGCTATAAAGAGGTCATCAGTATATGAAACAGCCCCCTGCTGCCATTCCTTATTTCCA 360
Sbjct 146236882	TTGGCTATAAAGAGGTCATCAGTATATGAAACAGCCCCCTGCTGCCATTCCTTATTTCCA 146236823
Query 361	TAGAAAAGCCTTGACTTGaggttagatttttttatattttgtttgttttttttttc 420
Sbjct 146236822	TAGAAAAGCCTTGACTTGAGGTTAGATTTTTTTTATATTTTGTGTTGTTATTTTTTC 146236763
Query 421	tttaacatcccTAAAATTTTCCTTACATGTTTTACTAGCCAGATTTTTCCTCCTCTCTG 480
Sbjct 146236762	TTTAACATCCCTAAAATTTTCCTTACATGTTTTACTAGCCAGATTTTTCCTCCTCTCTG 146236703
Query 481	ACTACTCCAGTCATAGCTGCCCTCTCTCTTATGGAGATC 522
Sbjct 146236702	ACTACTCCAGTCATAGCTGCCCTCTCTCTTATGGAGATC 146236661

Figure S-4. BLAST Alignments of 5' and 3' regions of the insert with corresponding regions of mouse PTH1R and rabbit beta globin genes. The sequences obtained for the 5' and 3' regions of the insert by Sanger sequencing were analyzed using the BLAST program at the National Center for Biotechnology Information web site and the mouse or rabbit genome data bases.

Figure S-5. Markers of bone and mineral metabolism in blood and urine of six-month-old Wild-type (WT) and hPTH1R-Ki (KI) mice separated by gender. Shown are data from **Figure 5** separated by female (**A-H**) and male (**I-P**) mice. Column heights and error bars indicates means \pm SD.

Figure S-6. Markers of bone and mineral metabolism in blood and urine of 13-month-old Wild-type (WT) and hPTH1R-Ki (KI) mice separated by gender. Shown are data from **Figure 6** separated by female (**A-H**) and male (**I-P**) mice. P values indicate significant differences between WT and KI mice. Column heights and error bars indicate means \pm SD. Dashed line in serum CTX-1 plots indicate the limit of detection (L.O.D.).

Figure S-7 Serum Blood Urea Nitrogen (BUN) at age six months and 13 months in WT and homozygous hPTH1R-Ki mice. Data in each group are means \pm SD of samples from 10 mice, of which 5 were female and 5 were male. Values from male and females within each genotype were not significantly different.

Table S-1 Micro-CT analysis of femurs from 6-month-old hPTH1R-KI and WT mice

	Females				Males			
	WT		KI		WT		KI	
		n		n		n		n
Length (mm)	15.8 + 0.23[#]	3	15.7 + 0.2	5	14.7 + 0.7	7	15.3 + 0.4	5
Distal metaphysis								
Trabecular bone volume (BV/TV, %)	3.82 + 1.38[#]	3	3.81 + 0.58[#]	5	10.6 + 3.9	7	11.5 + 4.2	5
Trabecular number (mm ⁻¹)	2.6 + 0.1[#]	3	2.3 + 0.2[#]	5	4.0 + 0.3	7	3.9 + 0.2	5
Trabecular Thickness (mm)	0.040 + 0.001	3	0.050 + 0.001	5	0.050 + 0.001	7	0.050 + 0.010	5
Mid-shaft								
Cortical bone area (BA/TA, %)	50.4 + 0.5[#]	3	50.9 + 1.04[#]	5	43.0 + 1.9	7	44.7 + 1.9	5
Cortical thickness (mm)	0.21 + 0.01[#]	3	0.20 + 0.01[#]	5	0.16 + 0.01	7	0.19 + 0.01*	5
Cortical porosity (%)	0.76 + 0.27	3	0.57 + 0.04[#]	5	1.38 + 1.30	5	0.84 + 0.22	5

Trabecular bone volume relative to tissue volume (BV/TV, %) at the metaphyses was measured in a 1.5 mm-thick region (150 adjacent cross-sectional planes, 0.01 mm/plane) interior to the cortices and extending from the edge of the growth plate towards the midshaft. Cortical bone area relative to tissue area (BA/TA, %) at the mid-shaft was measured as the mean of the areas of 50 adjacent cross-sectional planes (0.01 mm/plane) spanning a 0.5 mm-thick region. *, P = 0.032 for the difference between values from KI male vs. WT male mice (other differences between values from WT vs. KI mice of same gender were not significant). Data are means±SEM of the number of samples indicated (n); #, P < 0.05 for differences between values from male vs. female mice of same genotype.

Table S-2 Micro-CT analysis of femurs from 13-month-old hPTH1R-KI and WT mice

	Females				Males			
	WT		KI		WT		KI	
		n		n		n		n
Length (mm)	16.2 + 0.35[#]	5	15.5 + 0.2	5	14.6 + 0.5	5	15.3 + 0.2	5
Distal metaphysis								
Trabecular bone volume (BV/TV, %)	2.04 + 0.52[#]	5	1.72 + 0.38[#]	5	4.76 + 0.75	5	6.80 + 1.03	5
Trabecular number (mm ⁻¹)	1.7 + 0.18[#]	5	1.5 + 0.1[#]	5	3.1 + 0.1	5	2.9 + 0.1	5
Trabecular Thickness (mm)	0.056 + 0.002[#]	5	0.051 + 0.003[#]	5	0.046 + 0.001	5	0.050 + 0.001	5
Mid-shaft								
Cortical bone area (BA/TA, %)	43.1 + 0.9	5	44.2 + 1.24[#]	5	43.0 + 0.9	5	38.4 + 1.04*	5
Cortical thickness (mm)	0.18 + 0.01	5	0.18 + 0.01	5	0.17 + 0.01	5	0.17 + 0.01	5
Cortical porosity (%)	0.64 + 5.00	5	0.56 + 0.03	5	0.81 + 0.06	5	0.79 + 0.10	5

Trabecular bone volume relative to tissue volume (BV/TV, %) at the metaphyses was measured in a 1.5 mm-thick region (150 adjacent cross-sectional planes, 0.01 mm/plane) interior to the cortices and extending from the edge of the growth plate towards the midshaft. Cortical bone area relative to tissue area (BA/TA, %) at the mid-shaft was measured as the mean of the areas of 50 adjacent cross-sectional planes (0.01 mm/plane) spanning a 0.5 mm-thick region. *, P = 0.017 for the difference between values from KI male vs. WT male mice (other differences between values from WT vs. KI mice of same gender were not significant). Data are means±SEM of the number of samples indicated (n); #, P < 0.05 for differences between values from male vs. female